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Microstructural Characterization of Polymer Composites via X-ray CT

Research project

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Kaunas, 2024

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Introduction

Polymer composites are widely used in industries such as aviation and aerospace due to their light weight, low cost, and good mechanical properties. The main performance of composites is determined by the choice of fillers and how they are distributed in the polymer matrix. The addition of various fillers to strengthen or reinforce polymers is one of the main conditions. Various types of materials are used in this process, for example (carbon, glass, metal, textile, etc.). In addition, the shape, size and percentage of the fillers (fibers, microparticles, nanoparticles, etc.) play a key role. All of these are selected and determined according to the application areas and properties of the material. The compatibility between the polymer matrix and the filler varies according to the quality and properties of the composite materials and affects one hand. If this compatibility is not properly ensured, the durability of the material and its strength can be seriously weakened, so it is important to be careful in this matter. In order to obtain quality polymer composites, it is primarily necessary to study, test and then accurately select the polymer matrix, hardener, fillers and reinforcing materials in advance. After that, the synthesis and dispersion of the fillers must be carried out in a correct way, and then the production process must be carried out in accordance with standards and regulations.

1. Literature Review

1.1. Fillers and Polymer Matrix Composites

Starting with the Basic Properties of Fillers, Polymer fillers come in three states (solid, liquid and gas). These substances are distributed within the polymer matrix, creating a system consisting of different phases. The main purpose of adding fillers to polymers is to improve the properties of the material. Thanks to this process, the way to create strong polymer materials is further simplified. Costs are reduced and waste is recycled, and in some cases it is even used for decorative purposes.

There are four main types of fillers :

1. Dispersive fillers – these include materials such as talc, asbestos, aluminum hydroxide, and talc.
2. Fibrous fillers – consist of metallic, glass, carbon, boron, organic, and ceramic fibers.
3. Sheet fillers – materials such as fabric, paper, wood veneer, tapes, and meshes belong to this group.
4. Bulk fillers – consist of bulk pieces and frame systems

All of these fillers listed above ensure that polymeric materials are more durable and strong and at a more affordable price. They are especially popular in industrial fields due to their wide use.

As for polymer matrices, Polymer matrices are selected according to the intended use of the product. It should also be emphasized that matrix materials have a great influence on the properties of the composite, including (strength, heat and moisture resistance, resistance to aggressive environments and the method of production of the product). Polymers are used as matrices in two forms, in pure form (in the form of powder, granules, sheets, films), or in the form of a binder (synthetic polymer, hardener and hardening accelerator). In addition, solvents, colorants, plasticizers, stabilizers and other components are added to the binders during production to give them the necessary properties. Most often, thermosetting binders are used when producing reinforced plastics[1].

1.1.1. Disperse Fillers

According to the size of the particles, dispersed fillers are divided into 4 types: Coarsely dispersed (> 40 microns), medium dispersed (10-40 microns), highly dispersed (1-10 microns) and ultra-dispersed (< 1 micron). The choice of which filler varies depending on the application and requirements. More importantly, the shape of the particles directly affects the flowability of the polymer and the tension created inside it. Also, the coefficients vary depending on the shape: 3 for square-shaped particles, 2.5 for round particles, and 5 and higher for flat (plate) particles. As the shape of the particles becomes more complex, the viscosity of the polymer and the tension inside it also increase.

In addition to all of the above, the sedimentation of the fillers should be taken into account. If the density of the particles is low and the size is large, the fillers sediment more quickly. The surface area of fillers indicates how they interact with the polymer, for example, the larger the surface area, the better the interaction between the polymer and the filler. Surface area is measured by the surface area of 1 gram of filler and can vary between 0.01 m²/g and 300 m²/g.

The density of dispersed fillers is also an important characteristic and varies according to their type, as can be seen from the Table 1 below[1].

Table 1. Density of dispersed fillers[1].

Filler	Chemical Formula	Density (kg/m ³)
Kaolin	Al ₄ [Si ₂ O ₅] ₂ (OH) ₈	2600
Talc	Mg ₃ Si ₄ O ₁₀	2788
Chalk	CaCO ₃	2600-2900
Quartz (glass)	SiO ₂	2248
Barite	BaSO ₄	4480
Aerosil	SiO ₂	2350
Technical Carbon	C	1820
Rutile	TiO ₂	4200-4300

1.1.2. Filler Dispersion Effects on the Mechanical Properties

Along with the addition of fillers, there are noticeable changes in the tensile properties of glass fabric-reinforced epoxy (G-E) composites, in short, they change for the better. The filler-free G-E composite has a tensile strength of 305 MPa and a tensile modulus of 12.6 GPa. These properties will change if fillers are added. For example, when silicon carbide (SiC) filler is included in the composition of the composite, the tensile strength is 404.2 MPa, and the tensile modulus is 13.1 GPa. This is achieved by SiC filler being 10% of the total weight of the composite.

Graphite fillers are also used to improve the tensile properties, although if we compare this effect with SiC, it can be said that it is small. This improvement is due to the good adhesion of the epoxy and fillers to each other. Due to the adhesion, the stress is transferred to the fillers, making the material more durable and strong. The main factor affecting the distribution behavior is the size of the fillers. It can be observed from Figure.1 that SEM micrographs showing fiber removal and filler-matrix adhesion in SiC-filled G-E composites are presented. Note (a) Lower magnification 50× (b) Higher magnification 1500×.

Fig. 1.1 SEM images of filled and unfilled G-E specimens after tensile testing.[2]

Flexural Properties:

Addition of fillers has a role in improving the flexural properties to some extent. For example, the unfilled G-E composite has a flexural strength of 334.22 MPa and a flexural modulus of 21.23 GPa. The composite filled with 10% graphite has the highest flexural strength of 475.22 MPa and a flexural modulus of 26.94 GPa. Graphite fillers are evenly distributed in the epoxy matrix and have a lubricating effect, which helps in improving the flexural properties. Fillers distribute stress evenly and prevent crack propagation during flexural loading. However, at high filler contents, especially SiC, aggregation occurs, which leads to improper stress distribution. SEM images of fractures and micro-cracks formed during flexural loading are shown in Figure 1.2 and Figure 1.3[2].

Note (a) Lower magnification 50× (b) Higher magnification 1500×.

Fig. 1.1.2 SEM images of unfilled G-E samples that broke during bending tests.[3]

Fig. 1.1.3 SEM images of broken SiC-filled G-E samples after bending tests.[3]

Impact Strength :

If fillers are added, the impact strength of G-E composites begins to decrease. Simply put, the unfilled composite material has a higher impact strength. However, if graphite and silicon carbide (SiC) fillers are added, this indicator decreases. Graphite fillers cause a smaller decrease in impact strength, while SiC reduces impact strength more than others. We can say that these decreases are due to the voids formed in the matrix and the stress concentration created by the fillers. The hardness of SiC particles significantly increases the local stress during impact, causing more serious decreases. These changes are described in detail in the relevant graphs and images[3].

1.2. X-ray CT for 3D Filler Characterization

General Understanding of X-ray Computed Tomography : X-ray computed tomography is a useful technology that can show us the interior of an object or thing in 3D. The basic working principle allows us to analyze the density of the object without causing any damage to it. The main and fundamental principle of CT is that X-rays are attenuated as they pass through a material (some or all of the beam is absorbed by the object), allowing us to observe its interior.

The general equation for absorption is expressed as Fig. 1.4:

$$I(x) = I_0 * e^{-\int \mu(s) ds}$$

Fig. 1.1.4 absorption formula[4]

Where:

$I(x)$ – Intensity of the emitted X-ray beam,

I_0 – intensity of the initial X-ray beam,

$\mu(s)$ – absorption coefficient,

s – beam path.

There are various methods for studying the properties of a material, such as its density and absorption coefficient, one of which is a mathematical method called the Radon transform, which allows us to observe the internal properties of an object in the form of a two- or three-dimensional image.

The equation for the Radon transform is as shown below Fig. 1.5:

$$P = \ln(I/I(x)) = -\int \mu(s) ds$$

Fig. 1.1.5 the Radon transform formula [4]

Modern CT systems : Unlike older systems, modern CT systems use much higher resolution imaging, both computationally and industrially, using a variety of filtered iterative algorithms. The detector pixel sizes also provide clearer and more detailed images. Studies have shown that new systems can produce images with resolutions ranging from 50 micrometers to 1 micrometer.

Computer Laminography is used to analyze objects with non-standard shapes or limited access and which cannot be rotated a full 360°. This method is an alternative to CT. Thanks to this method, internal images of objects are obtained using angular projections. The advantages of this method are that it can be applied in places with space and location limitations and has high accuracy and, most importantly, it allows for fast imaging[4].

1.3. Image Analysis Techniques and Dispersion Metrics

Shearography Technique- The method called shearography is a widely known method in various engineering fields such as aerospace, aviation, automotive, and construction. This laser-based technique is used to identify cracks and defects on the surface of objects (metals and composite materials). The system is equipped with a CCD camera which provides complete image acquisition and digital processing Fig 1.6. In addition, the system is equipped with a piezoelectric transducer (PZT) for phase analysis. An infrared laser (Nd:YAG laser with a wavelength of 532 nm) is used to illuminate the sample. The basic principle is that the light from this laser is incident on the surface of the object and scattered, and all this is recorded by the camera and then collected before and after the voltage is applied. And to understand the changes occurring on the surface of the object, the phase difference is calculated, and separate methods are used for this.

Fig. 1.1.6 System setup diagram for shearography system[5]

As an example of all this, let's show the inspection of the rear fixed canopy of an A320 aircraft for cracks in the X and Y directions. During the inspection, a 500-watt infrared light was used to heat the sample, and defects ranging in size from 0.8 cm to 3.0 cm were detected[5].

Fig. 1.1.7 (a) X- Axes shearing and (b) Y-Axes shearing of A320

Infrared thermography- is one of the most widely used non-destructive testing (NDT) Fig. 1.8 methods that uses electromagnetic radiation. It has a wavelength from 700 nm to 1 mm. The only drawback here is that the main working principle of this method is based on heat dissipation, and since heat does not dissipate completely and properly in composite materials, it is difficult to detect defects in them[6].

Fig. 1.1.8 Sample image of infrared thermography device[6]

CT technology- Computed Tomography is an indispensable method for observing the external and internal structures of objects in various fields. The system can be said to consist of 4 parts: an X-ray source, its detector, a rotating table and a scanner for data analysis Fig. 1.9 .

Fig. 1.1.9 Industrial CT scanner[7]

The basic working principle of this system is to send photon beams at the object at specified angles. Some of these sent X-rays are absorbed by the object and based on the collected data, an internal image of the object is created[7].

Ultrasonic inspection - is a very convenient and non-destructive inspection method for inspecting the internal structures of materials or objects. In order to inspect the interior of objects, sound waves (0.5-25 MHz) are sent to them at certain values, and these waves lose a certain amount of energy when passing through the material. Then the reflected sounds are measured and recorded at the interfaces (pulse echo) or from the opposite surface (pulse transmission). and the returned defects clearly show us where they are. If we compare Ultrasonic inspection with radiography, we will see that Ultrasonic inspection has a greater penetrating power. It is capable of detecting defects deep within the steel, up to about 6-7 meters. The basic principle of ultrasonic testing is shown very clearly in Figure 2 [8].

Fig. 1.2 Basic components of an ultrasonic flaw detector[8]

Eddy Current Array (ECA) technology is one of the most widely used non-destructive inspection methods in the aviation industry to detect defects such as cracks and corrosion before they cause any accidents. Briefly, ECA consists of electronically controlling several eddy current sensors (coils) within a probe. This technology allows for a large area to be inspected in a single pass. This technology has already proven itself in the aviation industry and has become one of the most widely used methods. For example, when detecting subsurface cracks on the edge of the doubler on Boeing 737 aircraft, the ECA method is able to easily detect cracks with a length of 6 mm and a depth of 0.24 mm, as shown in Figure 1.2.1.[9]

Fig. 1.2.1 Location of doubler edge damage on 737 (left).[9]

In addition, it can be seen in C-scan images that cracks are very easily visible with color transitions, as an example of which we can look at Figure 1.2.2.

Fig. 1.2.2 ECA C-scan of Boeing 737 doubler edge showing subsurface cracks[9]

Overall, we can see from the research that ECA technology speeds up verification processes and provides us with a database that is stored and accessible at any time for research and analysis by encoding data[9].

2. Gaps and Challenges in Research

Dispersion Challenges - One of the main challenges we still face is ensuring complete uniform distribution in polymer matrices. If there is no proper distribution, it leads to a decrease in the properties of the material, or in other words, to its weakening. Although reactive extrusion provides some kind of intensive mixing and shearing forces, it is not possible to fully ensure this distribution, especially with nanoparticles at high concentrations.

Filler-Matrix Compatibility- Chemical modifications are required to ensure full compatibility with polymer matrices and fillers, all of which add to the process length and manufacturing cost. In addition, the different filler types required for these modifications are not always effective for the intended combinations, i.e., do not give the desired results.

Monitoring Filler Dispersion- It is very difficult to accurately monitor the distribution of fills in real time. These methods used today are not accurate and effective enough in this field.

Real-Time Monitoring: It is very difficult to accurately monitor the distribution of fillers in real time. These methods used today are not accurate and effective enough in this field. The next problem is **Process Optimization**, which is not easy to monitor different parameters at the same time and keep them in a certain balance, and finally, the **Scaling Challenges** that we face, which are problems in bringing laboratory processes to industrial level[10].

Limitations of X-ray CT- X-ray computed tomography often has difficulty detecting delaminations or microcracks or defects perpendicular to the beam direction. In addition, it is difficult to obtain sufficient contrast in carbon-reinforced composite materials. In terms of safety, CT emits a high dose of radiation, which makes it dangerous, and finally, it requires expensive equipment and significant computing power to reconstruct 3D models, which creates financial difficulties.

Limitations of Shearography - The main problem with optical interference-based shearography is that the surface of the object being tested must be somewhat rough (micro-imperfections). If the surface is too smooth, the light will not be reflected properly and the method will not give the desired results. The test environment has an effect on this process (e.g., vibration, lighting conditions) and this will have a certain effect on the result. Shearography mainly provides surface tension maps and has difficulty in detecting defects in the underlying layer, i.e., deeper defects, and cannot detect them effectively[11].

Gaps in Eddy Current Testing- One of the negative features of ECT is its sensitivity to changes in magnetic permeability, especially in ferromagnetic materials. In addition, ETC is not suitable for use with materials that are not electrically conductive, as it will give false results if applied. It is also not suitable for use with objects with large surfaces[12].

Disadvantages and Gaps of Ultrasonic Testing (UT) - Often ultrasonic waves are attenuated in composite materials, which seriously affects penetration. **Anisotropy Problem** Composite materials are heterogeneous and anisotropic, which allows ultrasonic waves to scatter and mode conversion. **Surface preparation for testing** is another problem, as it must be prepared for complete contact with the surface. Rough or irregular surfaces are obstacles to the transmission of ultrasonic waves[13].

Conclusions

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